

Modeling the activities of enterprises in the housing and communal services sector under conditions of probabilistic uncertainty

E.Y. Khrustalev,

д-р экон. наук, проф., главный научный сотрудник, Центральный экономико-математический институт РАН (e-mail: stalev777@yandex.ru)

S.N. Larin,

канд. техн. наук, старший научный сотрудник, ведущий научный сотрудник, Центральный экономико-математический институт РАН (e-mail: sergey77707@rambler.ru)

O.E. Khrustalev,

канд. экон. наук, старший научный сотрудник, Центральный экономико-математический институт РАН (e-mail: stalev777@yandex.ru)

Аннотация. Сфера ЖКХ сегодня представляет собой совокупность предприятий более тридцати видов экономической деятельности. Отношения между ними строятся на рыночных принципах. Вместе с тем в их деятельности имеется ряд ключевых особенностей. Они связаны с тем, что в условиях проведения комплексной модернизации инфраструктуры и активной рыночной трансформации этой сферы, при выработке управленческих решений необходимо учитывать одновременное воздействие множества разнонаправленных факторов. Это обстоятельство позволяет сделать предположение о том, что в практической деятельности предприятий сферы ЖКХ всегда присутствует вероятностная неопределенность. Поэтому, в качестве предмета настоящего исследования выбрана деятельность предприятий сферы ЖКХ, а также особенности принятия управленческих решений в условиях вероятностной неопределенности. Методологической основой нашего исследования стали методы экономико-математического моделирования, а именно: обоснование использования векторных критериев, задание предпочтений допустимых вероятностных распределений. В результате проведенных исследований были разработаны модели выбора и принятия управленческих решений предприятиями сферы ЖКХ с учетом факторов вероятностной неопределенности на основе задания их предпочтений на множестве допустимых вероятностных распределений случайного набора управленческих решений при симметричных и несимметричных распределениях. Предложенный подход и разработанные модели могут найти практическое применение в повседневной деятельности предприятий сферы ЖКХ.

Abstract. The housing and communal services sector today is a collection of enterprises of more than thirty types of economic activity. The relations between them are built on market principles. At the same time, there are a number of key features in their activities. They are related to the fact that in the conditions of comprehensive modernization of infrastructure and active market transformation of this sector, when developing management decisions, it is necessary to take into account the simultaneous impact of many multidirectional factors. This circumstance allows us to assume that probabilistic uncertainty is always present in the practical activities of enterprises in the housing and communal services sector. Therefore, the economic activity of enterprises in the housing and communal services sector, as well as the features of making management decisions in conditions of probabilistic uncertainty, were chosen as the subject of this study. The methodological basis of our study was the methods of economic and mathematical modeling, namely: justification of the use of vector criteria, setting preferences for admissible probability distributions. As a result of the conducted research, models of selection and adoption of management decisions by enterprises in the housing and communal services sector were developed taking into account the factors of probabilistic uncertainty based on the assignment of their preferences on a set of admissible probability distributions of a random set of management decisions with symmetric and asymmetric distributions. The proposed approach and the developed models can find practical application in the daily activities of enterprises in the housing and communal services sector.

Ключевые слова: жилищно-коммунальное хозяйство, предприятия, вероятностная неопределенность, принятие решений, симметричные и несимметричные распределения.

Keywords: housing and communal services, enterprises, probabilistic uncertainty, decision making, symmetric and asymmetric distributions.

Introduction

The housing and utilities sector is one of the socially significant sectors of the economy. The state

and development of the economic potential of any municipal, regional, or territorial complex largely depend on the level of its development, reliability, and

sustainability. It rightfully plays a decisive role in assessing the quality of life of the population. The housing and utilities sector can be identified as a complex system based on property relations. It includes enterprises of various types of economic activity, namely: suppliers of electricity, heat, hot and cold water, regional operators for major repairs and solid municipal waste (SMW) management, as well as management organizations and homeowners' associations. Ideally, the goal of their activities is to ensure that each apartment is always warm, light, the yard is clean and cozy, and, most importantly, that homeowners do not have to pay too much for it.

The housing and communal services sector is characterized by the provision of two types of services to homeowners: housing and utilities.

Housing services include everything that is necessary for the proper maintenance of the common property of the owners of premises in an apartment building (AB). A specific list of housing services is agreed upon by the owners and the management organization in the contract. Housing services include, for example:

- maintenance and repair of common property of owners of premises in an apartment building (inspections of common property, identification of damage and violations), including sanitary maintenance of common property (janitor services, services for cleaning entrances, their disinfection and deratization, services for cleaning garbage chutes);

- services for managing common property and common funds (reception, storage and transfer of technical documentation, filling in and updating information in the State Information System for Housing and Public Utilities, debt collection work, etc.);

- since January 2017, housing services also include utilities consumed for the proper maintenance of common property in an apartment building. This may include cold and hot water supply, water disposal, and electricity supply [1].

Responsibility for the proper provision of housing services in relation to an apartment building lies primarily with the owners of the premises in it. For the qualified provision of housing services, they choose one of three methods of managing the apartment building, namely: a management organization, a homeowners' association (HOA), or a person who has been chosen by the owners to implement the functions of direct management of the apartment building [2].

As part of the comprehensive monitoring in the housing and utilities sector from September to November 2023, the People's Front conducted an online survey among 15.9 thousand citizens in 87 regions of the Russian Federation. The survey results showed that about 80% of respondents live in apartment buildings. Up to 60% of respondents reported that they had encountered problems in the sphere of utilities, and due to the fault of management

organizations. 41% of citizens rated the condition of their home as satisfactory, poor, or not changing for the better, and 18% of respondents noticed a "significant deterioration". Only 10% of respondents reported an improvement in the condition of the building. A quarter of survey participants had problems with water supply over the past year, 23% of respondents - with heating. In 57% of cases, respondents named network accidents as the cause of interruptions. Moreover, over 40% of respondents spend 10 to 20% of their family income on paying for utilities, and up to 8% have debts for housing and communal services [3].

In October 2022, an important document was approved that determined the vector of development of the housing and communal services sector for years to come - "Strategy for the Development of the Construction Industry and Housing and Communal Services of the Russian Federation for the Period up to 2030 with a Forecast up to 2035". This document sets out the achievement of the rate of renewal of engineering infrastructure above 5% annually by 2030 [4].

Today in Russia there are about 74 thousand heat supply sources and about 8 thousand heat supply organizations, and in total there are about 13 thousand resource supply organizations. The public utilities sector consists of almost 950 thousand kilometers of networks, including 575 thousand kilometers of water supply networks, 200 thousand kilometers of wastewater networks and 168 thousand kilometers of heat supply networks. At the beginning of 2024, it was necessary to replace 42% of heat supply networks, 30% of water supply networks, 46.6% of wastewater networks [5, 6].

According to the Russian Ministry of Construction, 6482 incidents occurred at housing and communal services facilities from January 1 to December 31, 2023. In the previous year, there were 6491. That is, at about the same level. But at the same time, the number of accidents in the heat supply sector increased: there were 507 compared to 394 accidents last year for the same period [7].

When carrying out economic activities, housing and communal services enterprises, being economic entities, are unlikely to make decisions that may result in losses [8, 9]. On the contrary, the main goal of each economic entity in a market environment is to ensure its profitability. Only by receiving sufficient income can economic entities function and develop normally. To do this, they must make informed choices and take certain multi-criteria decisions when carrying out their activities in conditions of probabilistic uncertainty. The use of economic and mathematical modeling methods can play an important role in solving this problem.

Purpose of the study

The main objective of this study is to substantiate the use of existing methods of economic and

mathematical modeling for the selection of criterion indicators and the development of models that allow housing and communal services enterprises to make management decisions in specific situations. The authors believe that to achieve this, it is necessary to take into account the factors of probabilistic uncertainty based on the assignment of their preferences on a set of admissible probability distributions of a random set of decisions with symmetric and asymmetric distributions.

Materials and methods of research

The toolkit for forming a model of choice and decision-making under conditions of probabilistic uncertainty can be based on determining the preferences of an economic entity on a set of admissible probability distributions of a random set of decisions [10, 11]. Let us assume that each decision r in a certain set $R = \{R\}$ of admissible probability distributions is a random variable. Further, we will assume that all descriptions of random variables can be applied practically without changes to random vectors.

Then the problem of choosing and making a decision for random variables can be represented as the problem of forming a vector criterion $I(r, y) = (I_1(r, y), \dots, I_n(r, y))$, where $r \in R$ is a set of admissible solutions, $y \in Y$ are uncertainty factors. In this case, if we consider each uncertainty factor y to be a random parameter on the set Y , then the vector criterion $I(r, y)$ can also be considered a random variable.

In the following reasoning we will proceed from the fact that the admissible solution r as a random variable is equivalent to some random income d . Then the problem of choice and decision-making consists in maximizing this income. For this purpose it is necessary that preferences be specified for the economic agent on the set $R = \{R\}$ of admissible probability distributions, that is, the concept of "distribution R is "better" than distribution K " is defined. We will denote the preference relation by the expression $R \succ K$. The preference relation can be calculated if there is a functional F defined on the set R such that $R \succ K \Leftrightarrow F(R) \geq F(K)$.

We will call the functional F a preference indicator, since its meaning is that for computable preference relations, each distribution can be assigned a certain number. In the future, we will compare these distributions by comparing the specified numbers. In this case, preferences on the set of distributions will be given by a natural order on the set of real numbers [12].

If a preference indicator exists, then any strictly increasing function of it will yield the same preference indicator, since the preference itself remains the same, and only the scale of the distribution evaluation changes. The converse will also be true: if there are two indicators of the same preference U and V , then there exists a strictly increasing function q such that $V = q(U)$. This means that preference

indicators of this kind are always defined up to a strictly monotone transformation.

A necessary and sufficient condition for a certain relation to be specified by an indicator is the restriction of the characteristics of the distribution of a random variable to only the first two parameters, namely: its mathematical expectation m and dispersion σ^2 . If we are interested in the distribution of random income d of some economic entities, then it will be quite natural to choose a distribution with a larger mathematical expectation m , and in the case of equality of mathematical expectations, to choose a distribution with a smaller dispersion σ^2 . However, in practice, there are no numerical functions to specify such a relation; no preference is possible. To get out of this situation, we formalize a number of requirements for determining the preferences of an economic entity on a set of admissible probability distributions of a random set of solutions.

Let us assume that d_{x_0} is a distribution concentrated at the point x_0 . In this case, we are dealing with a degenerate distribution, since the random variable we are considering is in fact deterministic and can take only one value x_0 . However, this circumstance does not prevent us from formally including this deterministic variable in the set of random variables. Now, if we assume that the random variable describes some income of an economic entity, then the condition $x_0 \geq x_1 \Rightarrow d_{x_0} \succ d_{x_1}$ means that with an increase in income, the distribution improves. In our case, the distribution functions d_{x_0} and d_{x_1} are related by the relation $d_{x_0}(x) \leq d_{x_1}(x)$ for all x . In what follows, we will use the statement that "distribution R is better than distribution K " ($R \succ K$) meant, that is:

$$R(x) \leq K(x) \quad (1)$$

for all x and all distributions, including degenerate ones.

Condition (1) will be considered a condition of stochastic dominance. In the practical activities of economic entities, it reflects their desire to increase income d .

In order to consider the assumptions associated with the desire for income "stability", we introduce a number of additional concepts. Thus, we will assume that the distribution of R is symmetric with the center of symmetry m if for all $x > 0$ the equality holds:

$$R(m-x) = 1 - R(m+x+0). \quad (2)$$

For a random variable of income d with distribution R , this condition means that the following relationship between probabilities holds:

$$P\{(d-m) > x\} = P\{(d-m) < -x\}, \quad (3)$$

that is, the probabilities of deviations of the random variable of income d from the center of symmetry in any direction will be equal to each other.

The above assumptions allow us to formalize the condition of "stability" of income of an enterprise

in the housing and communal services sector as follows.

Let R and K be symmetric distributions with a common center of symmetry m and let the following condition hold for $x \leq m$:

$$R(x) \leq K(x) \Rightarrow R \succ K. \quad (4)$$

In practice, condition (4) means that if there is a random variable ξ with distribution R , a random variable k with distribution K , and these distributions are symmetric with a common center of symmetry m , then for all $x > 0$ the condition will be satisfied:

$$P\{|d - m| > x\} \leq P\{|k - m| > x\}. \quad (5)$$

In other words, if R is a normal distribution with mean m and variance σ_1^2 , and K is a normal distribution with the same mean m and variance $\sigma_2^2 > \sigma_1^2$, then the condition for striving for stability will be the preference of the distribution of R over the distribution of K . Thus, conditions (4) and (5) are consistent with the requirement of stability [13]. This means that the problem of choice and decision-making by an economic entity to obtain a certain income under conditions of probabilistic uncertainty with symmetric distributions of random variables has a solution.

However, practice shows that this is a fairly simple case. A more complex case is the choice and adoption by an economic entity in the housing and utilities sector of decisions to obtain some income under conditions of probabilistic uncertainty with asymmetric distributions or distributions with different centers of symmetry. Indeed, if it is necessary to compare two normal distributions with the parameters of mathematical expectation and dispersion of the following type, respectively, (m_1, σ_1^2) and (m_2, σ_2^2) , then the economic entity must somehow correlate the desire to increase the mathematical expectation m (increase income) and reduce the dispersion σ^2 (increase stability).

This problem can be solved by defining a preference indicator on the set of admissible probability distributions of a random set of solutions and a utility function. In this case, it is advisable to choose the average value of the utility function as a preference indicator on the set of probability distributions [14]. Thus, we obtain the following expression:

$$F(R) = \int g(d) dR(d), \quad (6)$$

where $g(d)$ – utility function.

Expression (6) has the property that for any two numbers $\alpha \geq 0, \beta \geq 0, \alpha + \beta = 1$ the following equality will always exist:

$$F(\alpha R + \beta K) = \alpha F(R) + \beta F(K). \quad (7)$$

In the practical activities of an economic entity, expression (7) can be interpreted as follows. If an

economic entity chooses two options for obtaining income – with probability α and with distribution R (1) and with probability β and with distribution K (2), then the final distribution of income for it will be equivalent to a mixed distribution $(\alpha R + \beta K)$.

If the value of income d is considered a random variable, then it can be argued that the economic entity does not strive to make risky decisions, provided that

$$g(md) > mg(d), \quad (8)$$

and is prone to risk in case

$$g(md) < mg(d), \quad (9)$$

where m – mathematical expectation symbol, a $g(d)$ – utility function.

In other words, an economic agent that is not inclined to take risky decisions will prefer a decision for which the utility of average income will exceed the average utility of income. Conversely, an economic agent inclined to take risky decisions will strive to take the opposite decision.

At first glance, it seems that the use of the preference indicator (6) looks quite justified when comparing asymmetric distributions or distributions with different centers of symmetry. However, it is not always acceptable, since it is a linear functional.

To get out of such situations, it is advisable to use nonlinear functionals as a preference indicator. Let us consider one of the approaches to constructing such functionals. Let us introduce the “comparative utility” function $h(u, v)$, which shows how much income u seems “better” to an economic agent than income v . In this case, we will assume that for $u \geq v$ $h(u, v) \geq 0$, and for $u \leq v$ $h(u, v) \leq 0$.

Let us assume that the random variable of income d has the distribution R . Then the average comparative utility of the random income of an economic agent d in relation to his deterministic income v can be expressed as follows:

$$g(v) = mh(d, v) = \int h(x, v) dR(x) \quad (10)$$

Next, we will use the root of the equation $F(R)$ as an indicator of preference:

$$g(v) = 0 \quad (11)$$

Expression (5) represents the deterministic income v of an economic agent whose comparative utility in relation to random income d will always be zero on average. In other words, the deterministic income v is equivalent on average to the random income of the economic agent d .

If we assume that $h(u, v) = \omega(u)(f(u) - f(v))$, where $\omega(u)$ is some weight function, then the solution to equation (6) will have the following form:

$$F(R) = f^{-1} \left(\frac{\int f(u) \omega(u) dR(u)}{\int \omega(u) dR(u)} \right) \quad (12)$$

where f^{-1} – inverse function.

After the formalization, all the above justifications for the expressions "income d_1 is better than income d_2 " can be applied to vector criteria, since the conditions under which "vector I_1 is better than vector I_2 " have already been determined. Therefore, all considerations regarding the construction of a preference indicator under conditions of probabilistic uncertainty can be transferred to the case of a vector criterion I . In this case, we will already be talking about the distribution of a random vector I and the corresponding multidimensional utility function.

Results and discussion

As a result of the conducted research, the possibility of using existing tools by economic entities in the housing and utilities sector for forming a model of choice and decision-making taking into account probabilistic uncertainty factors was substantiated. For this purpose, it was proposed to use definitions of preferences of an economic entity on a set of admissible probabilistic distributions of a random set of decisions with symmetric and asymmetric distributions.

Conclusion

Our research allows us to draw the following conclusions.

1. Housing and communal services is a complex of interconnected spheres of activity that ensure stable and uninterrupted functioning of the life support system of the population.
2. Models for selecting and making management decisions have been developed taking into account factors of probabilistic uncertainty.
3. Preferences of enterprises in the housing and communal services sector on a set of admissible probability distributions of a random set of management decisions with symmetric and asymmetric distributions have been selected as criterion indicators.
4. The proposed models can find practical application in the daily activities of enterprises in the housing and communal services sector.

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